

Title: Using Social Media To Determine Outcomes That Matter Most To Patients

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Figure 1: Social media can be a valuable source of information throughout the product life cycle

Figure 2: Data collection and classification

Figure 3: Most commonly discussed topics on Twitter and Forums amongst BC patients

Figure 4: Most commonly reported concepts with HSI posts on Twitter and Forums amongst BC patients (excluding *Nonspecific reaction* and *Unevaluable event*)

Figure 5: Difference of means and 95% HPD for posts mentioning peripheral neuropathy compared with posts that mention other side effects

Figure 6: Difference of means and 95% HPD for posts mentioning Alopecia compared with posts that mention other side effects

Figure 7: Difference of means and 95% HPD for posts mentioning pain and pain in extremity compared with posts that mention other side effects

Table 1: Example of MedDRA term and vernacular synonyms

MedDRA preferred term	Synonyms
Rhinorrhoea	runny nose, congested, congestion, nose runny, nose running, nose runnin, snotty nose, snot, sniffly, sniffles, running nose, my nose run, nose run, stuffy

Table 2: Examples of positive, negative, neutral, and mixed sentiment posts

Sentiment Classification	Example Post
Positive	“I love chemo for making my quality of life better, worth the headaches.”
Negative	“ Chemo is truly not worth the side effects.”
Neutral	“No one will admit chemo is what’s caused my feet past 1.5yr 24HR day neuropathy.”
Mixed Sentiment	“Was wondering why pain’s up to an 8. Right. chemo day. I love what it does for me, but injection day’s a bit rough.”

Table 3: User experience topic volumes

MedDRA® Preferred Term	COUNT (%)
Emotional impact	46.05
Infection/immunity	37.41
Insurance	11.77
Employment	2.53
HCP distrust	0.89
Mobility	0.75
Treatment duration	0.30
Treatment interruption	0.30